

**SELECTION OF PRODUCTIVE LINES OF WINTER CHICKPEA FOR
DRYLAND AREAS**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7021137>

Abstract

One of the main factors that increase the productivity of dry lands is the rotation of grain crops with legumes. The pods and grains in one plant of winter Chickpea cultivars and cultivars planted in irrigated fields were analyzed, 12 cultivars were selected from 36 cultivars and selected cultivars were recommended for breeding.

Key words: winter chickpea, plant, variety, line, pods, seeds.

The main criterion of the State program of agricultural development is to increase the productivity of crops, agricultural culture and soil fertility by introducing the most modern intensive technologies of production, and applying modern agrotechnical rules and requirements to farming.

Special attention is being paid to the development of the agriculture of our country, the widespread introduction of scientific approaches and advanced modern technologies in this sector, ensuring food safety, increasing the production of fruits and vegetables, rice, grains and grain products, import-export issues. In this regard, unproductive cotton areas are reduced, vines and orchards are expanded, and grain leguminous areas are expanded, and high and quality products are obtained. In the 2017-2021 action strategy for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan, "... consistent development of agricultural production, further strengthening of the country's food security, intensive methods in the field of agricultural production, first of all, modern agro-technologies that save water and other resources implementation..." and other tasks are defined.

In 2018, 6.2 thousand tons of Chickpea grain were exported in our republic, and by 2021, the indicator is planned to increase by 19.2 thousand tons or by 310.2% compared to 2018.

Based on these tasks, it is important to choose Chickpea varieties suitable for different environmental conditions and to coordinate their cultivation technology based on variety characteristics in order to satisfy the population's demand for grains and grain products. Increasing the plant's winter resistance and achieving a high and high-quality grain yield by choosing the right planting time and depth, especially in autumn, are urgent problems [2].

One of such leguminous crops is Chickpeas. Because it has been proven in experiments that planting spiked grain crops after Chickpeas increases the amount of yield per hectare by 40-60% and accumulates biological nitrogen in the soil by 50 ha/kg on average, which is equivalent to applying 6-8 ha/t of rotted manure [1, 3].

Chickpeas are more nutritious than most other legumes, containing 20.1-32.4% protein. Amino acids contained in Chickpeas are unique and distinguished by their ability to eliminate various harmful and pathological factors in the human body. Chickpeas contain a lot of phosphorus, potassium, magnesium elements, lecithin, riboflavin (vitamin B2), nicotinic and panthenic acid, choline, and vitamin C. Being rich in amino acids asparagine and glutamine, Chickpea grain replaces meat in the human diet. For this reason, two-thirds of the Chickpeas grown in the world are consumed as food [4].

Chickpea is a valuable leguminous plant used in the national economy for various purposes. Chickpeas are mainly used as a food product. Light-colored varieties of Chickpeas are grown for food, and dark-grained varieties are grown for livestock [5].

Chickpea seeds are rich in protein, unlike other legumes. According to data, the grain of leguminous crops (dry matter) contains the following amount of protein: 27-28% in sorghum, 28-30% in chechevitsa, 24-25% in beans, 38-41% in soybeans, and 18-32% in Chickpeas. reported to be at most 32% protein and 8% fat [6, 7].

Chickpea grain is distinguished by its delicacy. Chickpea protein contains unique amino acids such as lysine, arginine, histidine, tyrazine, cysteine, etc., which are essential for the body of humans and livestock. These amino acids cannot be synthesized by the body itself, so it is obtained through food.

Chickpeas belong to the genus *Cicer*. There are 27 species in this category. 4 of them are annuals, and one of the 4 is a cultural species - *Cicer arietinum*. In addition to the cultivated species, there are 6 wild species in the CIS: 4 in Central Asia (*C. flexuosum* Lipsky, *C. macrocanthim* M. Pop, *C. songoricum* Steph, *C. pungens* Boiss), two in the Caucasus (*C. ervoides* (Silb) Fenzl and *C. anatolicum*

Aleph) occurs. These species are distributed in mountainous dry stony slopes and produce large vegetative masses and pods that burst when ripe. The use of these species as starting material has not been determined due to the cracking of the pods. All local and selective varieties of Chickpeas are divided into the following ecological groups.

The variety and its characteristics are of great importance in obtaining a high yield from agricultural crops. The introduction of high-yielding varieties of Chickpeas into production led to a several-fold increase in productivity in the following years.

Productivity of plants is the main criterion in the evaluation of selective varieties. The grain yield of Chickpeas is formed depending on several environmental conditions that affect its quantity and quality.

Chickpeas are more nutritious than most legumes and contain 20.1-32.4% protein. The amino acids contained in Chickpeas are unique and stand out for eliminating various harmful and pathological factors in the human body. Chickpeas are rich in phosphorus, potassium, magnesium, lecithin, riboflavin (vitamin B2), nicotine and panthate, choline, and vitamin C. Chickpeas are rich in aparagine and glutamine amino acids, replacing meat in the diet. Therefore, two-thirds of the Chickpeas grown in the world are consumed as food.

The difference between varieties in terms of productivity is an important indicator, and their research should be carried out depending on the external environmental conditions. The main requirement for the variety is high productivity in growing conditions.

Table 1

Yield structure of winter chickpea varieties and lines, against 2022.

No	Plots	Name	Number of pods of per plant				Number of grains of per plant
			1 seed	2 seed	3 seed	Total pods	
1	12	X04TH146/FLIP00-16XFLIP98-229	23	3	1	27	32
2	15	X04TH151/S01020XFLIP95-68	19	4	1	24	30
3	20	X04TH63/X03TH-131XFLIP99-34	17	2		19	21
4	21	X04TH147/FLIP00-17XFLIP98-230	22	3	1	26	31

5	35	X04TH164/FLIP 87-59CXFLIP99-34	24	2	1	27	31
6	45	X04TH138/FLIP98-22XFLIP95-51	24	3	2	29	32
7	63	X04TH172/ICCV-2XS01098	21	2	1	24	28
8	64	X04TH164/FLIP 87-59CXFLIP99-34	23	2	1	26	30
9	93	X05TH192/ICCV03108XFLIP00-06	19	2		21	23
10	94	X04TH136/FLIP97-229XFLIP97-126	20	2	1	23	27
11	117	X04TH57/X03TH-57XFLIP97-116	20	3	1	24	29
12	118	X04TH178/FLIP97-91XFLIP98-137	22	3	1	26	31

When the number of pods in one type of plant was calculated, 2-grain pods were 4 per pod, 3-grain pods were 1, and 1-grain pods were 17-24. The total number of pods in one plant was found to be from 19 pods to 27 pods.

According to the results of the analysis, it was calculated that the number of grains in one plant in the nursery is from 21 to 32. The yield indicators of samples that produced high grain were analyzed.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the pods and grains of one plant of winter pea varieties and ridges planted in dry areas were analyzed, and 12 lines were selected from 36 varieties and lines and recommended for selection work.

References:

1. Singh K. B. Chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* L.) //Field crops research. – 1997. – T. 53. – №. 1-3. – С. 161-170.
2. Kayumov N. S., Dilmurodov S. D. Selection of heat and drought tolerant varieties and lines of chickpea for rainfed areas //Высокие технологии, наука и образование: актуальные вопросы, достижения и инновации. – 2020. – С. 129-131.
3. Shakirjanovich K. N., Dilmurodovich D. S. Analysis of yield and protein content of drought-resistant chickpea lines for rainfed areas //International journal of discourse on innovation, integration and education. – 2021. – T. 2. – №. 1. – С. 108-111.

4. Файзуллаева Д., Каюмов Н. Ш., Дилмуродов Ш. Д. Лалмикор майдонлар учун нўхатнинг эртапишар тизмалари селекцияси //Молодой ученый. – 2020. – №. 34. – С. 161-163.

5. Abdimajidov J. et al. SELECTION OF DROUGHT-RESISTANT LINES OF LENTILS IN RAINFED AREAS //British Journal of Global Ecology and Sustainable Development. – 2022. – Т. 2. – С. 74-79.

6. Jukanti A. K. et al. Nutritional quality and health benefits of chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* L.): a review //British Journal of Nutrition. – 2012. – Т. 108. – №. S1. – С. S11-S26.

7. Ahmad F., Gaur P. M., Croser J. Chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* l.) //Genetic resources, chromosome engineering, and crop improvement-grain legumes. – 2005. – Т. 1. – С. 187-217.

